

Received:
2025/06/24
Accepted:
2025/07/22
Published:
2025/08/22

RESEARCH PAPER

OPEN ACCESS

Assessment of Potential Soil and Water Conservation Activities in Small Catchment Areas using Geospatial Techniques

Vikas Vatsa^{1*} and Nilanjana Roy²

¹Climate Change Expert, Watershed Management Directorate, Uttarakhand

²Social and Environmental Management Society, Uttarakhand

*Correspondence for materials should be addressed to VV (email: vatsavikas@gmail.com)

Abstract

Watershed management is a complex process that involves understanding the various components of a watershed and how they interact with one another. Drainage line treatment is an important aspect of watershed management, as it involves identifying areas where water is flowing and taking measures to prevent erosion and sedimentation. In recent years, remote sensing and Geographic Information System (GIS) technologies have been increasingly used for watershed management, including identifying potential activity zones and implementing soil and water conservation measures. The study aims to investigate remote sensing and GIS techniques for identifying watershed activities, especially drainage line treatment, in a small catchment area.

Keywords: Micro-watershed; Drainage Line Treatment; Geospatial techniques; Water conservation; Catchment areas

Introduction

The conservation and sustainable management of degraded natural resources—particularly soil, vegetation, and water—are essential for enhancing agricultural productivity, supporting multi-cropping systems, and ensuring sustainable livelihoods in watershed areas. Watershed management, especially in ecologically fragile and topographically complex regions, requires an integrated approach that considers agroclimatic zones, natural resource availability, and land use/land cover (LULC) characteristics to prioritize and implement soil and water conservation (SWC) measures.

Effective planning of SWC interventions within a watershed, such as drainage line treatments, is often challenged by the inaccessibility and economic constraints associated with delineating potential activity zones (Azari and Sepehr, 2018). In this context, Remote Sensing (RS) and Geographic Information System (GIS) technologies offer powerful tools to support the identification, planning, and monitoring of conservation interventions. Numerous studies have demonstrated the utility of geospatial techniques in delineating suitable sites for SWC measures, including artificial recharge zones and runoff management structures (Pandey et al., 2011).

Drainage line treatment—an integral component of watershed management—plays a crucial role in enhancing groundwater recharge, reducing soil erosion, moderating runoff, and improving overall water quality (Jain et al., 2020). Particularly in micro-watersheds, which serve as fundamental hydrological units, targeted treatment of drainage lines can significantly influence the hydrological balance and ecological sustainability of the larger watershed system. However, comprehensive planning in such areas necessitates a multidisciplinary understanding of the interactions between land use, topography, hydrological processes, and environmental quality (Zhao et al., 2025; Javarayigowda et al., 2018).

Geospatial tools facilitate spatial analysis and hydrological modelling to evaluate drainage networks, simulate runoff behaviour, and identify critical zones for intervention (Ahmed &

Shabana, 2020). Their application is especially relevant for resource-constrained and ecologically sensitive regions, where optimal allocation of financial and physical resources is paramount. Furthermore, integrating land use, slope, and drainage characteristics through RS-GIS techniques enables the development of effective conservation strategies that align with the principles of sustainable watershed development (Premanand et al., 2018; Mehra and Mehra, 2012).

This study explores the application of remote sensing and GIS techniques for identifying and planning drainage line treatments in the Bidhalana micro-watershed, which is part of the Song sub-watershed in Dehradun district, Uttarakhand, India. Conducted under the World Bank-funded Uttarakhand Decentralized Watershed Development Project (GRAMYA-II), the research aims to demonstrate how geospatial approaches can support data-driven decision-making for watershed conservation. By integrating hydrological modelling and spatial analysis, the study seeks to elucidate the influence of LULC and topography on surface runoff, sediment transport, and water infiltration, ultimately contributing to more effective and sustainable watershed management practices.

Study area

The Bidhalana MWS is located between 30°01'8.6"N-30°13'0"N latitudes and 78°0'12"E-78°17'0"E longitudes, covering a total geographical area of 2417 ha which falls in Raipur development block, Tehsil Rishikesh of district Dehradun (Fig. 1). The altitude ranges from 620m to 1890m above mean sea level (MSL). About, 70% of the study area is of more than 30% slope class. The top portion of the watershed has upright ridges that exhibit extremely precipitous slopes, manifesting signs of severe erosion, debris generation and accumulation at the foot of the slope. Soils of Bidhalna MWS are mostly loam to sandy loam. They are shallow to deep occurring on steep sloping mountainous terrain developed over shale, granite, gneiss, and limestone. Average Annual Rainfall varies from 1000 mm to 1200 mm and sometimes becomes hefty causing landslides. (WMD, 2014).

Fig. 1. Location of Bidhalana Micro-watershed

The area lies in the outer Himalayas and has a fragile environment. With the rise in human and cattle populations in the region, the burden on land has increased considerably. The demand of fuel wood, fodder, grazing and other socio-economic activities has increased many-fold over the years, causing a severe imbalance in the ecosystem. This added to faulty agricultural practices, improper land use and unplanned development works etc. coupled with unstable geological formations, has resulted in an accelerated rate of erosion (Gupta et al., 2017).

Methodology

To determine the potential zone of drainage line treatment in a micro watershed, the following components were taken: Drainage order, Land Use Land Cover (LULC), and Erosion intensity. ESRI Arc Map and Open source QGIS software were used for the analysis. The methodology for preparing Drainage line treatment was outlined in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Methodology for drainage line treatment

The CartoSat Digital elevation model (DEM) was used to derive slope, aspect, and flow accumulation maps. The Hydrology Tool in ArcGIS generated the stream network and derived drainage order maps of the Micro-watershed.

The IRS-LISS-IV MX satellite data was used to classify the land use/ land cover (LULC) map of the study area. The hybrid classification technique was used where a total of 50 classes were classified using unsupervised classification. Merging of similar classes into 6 major LULC classes than Supervised classification was also carried out to identify LULC classes. Both the unsupervised and supervised classified images along with ground truthing were used to finalize the LULC map of the study area. The major LULC classes were forest, agriculture, urban, water, barren and scrub. Soil erosion intensity assessment was done by giving weightage to drainage, LULC, Slope and forest density map of the study area (Vatsa et al., 2019). The final soil erosion intensity map (Fig. 4) was verified by ground truthing and rectified accordingly.

Fig. 3a. Elevation Map of Bidhalana MWS

Fig. 3b. Slope Map of Bidhalana MWS

Fig. 3c. Aspect Map of Bidhalana MWS

Fig. 3d. Drainage Map of Bidhalana MWS

Fig. 3e. Drainage Order Map of Bidhalana MWS

Fig. 3f. Land Use / Land Cover Map of Bidhalana MWS

Fig. 4. Erosion Intensity Map of Bidhalana MWS

Field data and Participatory Rural Appraisal (PRA) exercise was done for the assessment of the proposed watershed activity map of the study area. The final step involved the generation of potential zone for drainage line treatment through GIS modelling shown in Fig.5.

Fig. 5. Potential sites for drainage line treatment activities (Map of Bidhalana MWS)

Discussion and conclusion

The study shows that geospatial techniques can be a useful tool for assessing potential zones of drainage line activities and soil and water conservation activities in small catchment areas. The study highlights the importance of such techniques in identifying areas that are susceptible to soil erosion and degradation, and subsequently, prioritizing conservation activities. Moreover, the study demonstrates that geospatial techniques can provide a cost-effective and efficient means of identifying areas for conservation activities, which is particularly important in small catchment areas where resources may be limited. Despite the potential benefits of remote sensing and GIS for watershed management, their use still has technological challenges. One challenge is the need for high-quality, high-resolution data, which can be costly and difficult to obtain in some areas. Additionally, there is a need for improved data analysis and interpretation methods to use Geospatial techniques for watershed management effectively.

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Author Contributions

VV and NR conceived the concept, wrote and approved the manuscript.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to express their sincere gratitude to the Project Director of the Watershed Management Directorate, Dehradun, for his invaluable support and guidance throughout this research. The authors also acknowledge Watershed Management Directorate, Dehradun for providing the necessary facilities and resources to conduct this study.

Funding

This work was supported by the Watershed Management Directorate, Dehradun.

Availability of data and materials

Not applicable.

Competing interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Ethics approval

Not applicable.

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Citation: Vatsa V and Roy N (2025) Assessment of Potential Soil and Water Conservation Activities in Small Catchment Areas using Geospatial Techniques. *Environmental Science Archives* 4(2): 559–564.